

IMPACT

Robotic surgery in the NHS: building high-performance robotic programmes

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The debate about robotic surgery in the NHS centres on platforms: which one to choose, what it costs, and how best to maintain case volume. However, this framing can overlook the more fundamental issue of the overall hospital programme. At West Hertfordshire Teaching Hospitals (WHTH), improvements in colorectal cancer outcomes have been driven by both adoption of robotic technology and the systems, processes, training pathways, and multidisciplinary culture built around it.

In 2022, the department adopted the CMR Versius platform. In 100 consecutive colorectal cancer resections, lymph node yields were ≥ 12 in 95% of cases compared to 88% nationally, with comparable margin positivity and no safety deterioration.¹ The finding was reassuring but not surprising, as robotics can match laparoscopic outcomes with adequate training and case volume, and the barrier to entry is lower than assumed.

Figure 1. Surgeon operating at the Da Vinci 5 console during a robotic colorectal cancer resection at West Hertfordshire Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust.

As the department scaled robotic surgery, it became the default platform for elective colorectal cancer rather than the exception.

When most cases are performed robotically, workflows stabilise, teams develop muscle memory, and variation reduces. Our com-

parative analysis of 290 patients across laparoscopic, Versius, and da Vinci approaches revealed important differences in outcomes.² Length of stay fell from a median of 5 days with laparoscopy to 4 days with da Vinci; the probability of prolonged stay beyond five days dropped from 49% to 22%. Outcomes with Versius were intermediate at 37.5%. While programme maturity undoubtedly influences performance, these findings suggest that differences in platform design, workflow integration, and surgeon experience may also contribute to observed variation.

Conventional wisdom states that robotics increases operating time and therefore reduces efficiency, and this may be true during early adoption. However, our pattern reversed this trend as the department's experience matured. In our comparative analysis, da Vinci operative times were similar to laparoscopy after adjustment, despite more complex dissection.² More importantly, variability reduced and predictability improved — a standardised operation that consistently takes two hours is more valuable to a system than one fluctuating between 90 minutes and three hours.

Figure 2. Clinical outcomes and associated healthcare costs following minimally invasive colorectal cancer resection performed using the da Vinci system, Versius system, and conventional laparoscopy.² LOS = length of stay; ICU = intensive care unit.

Figure 3. Comparison of total operative time (minutes) for minimally invasive colorectal cancer resection performed using the da Vinci system (n=102), Versius system (n=103), and conventional laparoscopy (n=85).²

Our standardisation enabled technique innovation, demonstrated by our adoption of intracorporeal anastomosis for right hemicolectomy. In 163 patients, intracorporeal anastomosis was associated with a 24% reduction in total length of stay, a 53% reduction in in-hospital stay, and significantly lower odds of

overall postoperative complications (OR 0.30, 95% CI 0.16–0.55; $p < 0.001$), with a 31.6 mg/L reduction in day one C-reactive protein.³ The cost was an additional 21 minutes in theatre — not inefficiency, but investment, since the time spent in theatre was offset by time saved on the ward.

Figure 4. Inverse probability of treatment weighting-adjusted comparison of postoperative length of stay between extracorporeal anastomosis (ECA) and intracorporeal anastomosis (ICA) following minimally invasive right hemicolectomy. Total LOS was 24.0% shorter in the ICA group ($p<0.001$). ICA was independently associated with significantly lower odds of overall postoperative complications (OR 0.30, 95% CI 0.16–0.55; $p<0.001$).³

We can directly address the learning curve argument with our department's experience. In the first year with Versius, high-volume surgeons achieved a 35% reduction in operative time despite increasing console utilisation.¹ With da Vinci Xi, learning curves stabilised after approximately 12 right hemicolectomies and 20 pelvic resections.⁴ Junior trainees performed as well as senior trainees in some domains, challenging the assumption that robotic training should be deferred until independent practice. We embedded a structured training programme for residents within service delivery rather than treating it as optional. Residents completed simulation modules in a median of 4.5 days, participated in 43 cases without complication, and reported high satisfaction.⁵

The introduction of a Virtual Hospital pathway extended minimally invasive benefits beyond discharge. Inpatient length of stay fell from 4 days to 2 days; Days Alive and at Home within 30 days increased from 25.5 to 28.6. Over 90% of patients preferred home-based recovery.⁶

The department's performance against national benchmarking reflects this cumulative alignment. Model Health System data for

2025 shows prolonged length of stay beyond nine days was approximately 4% at WHTH compared to 21% nationally, with no increase in readmissions.⁷

Outliers in this setting require examination, and ours reflects not a single innovation but the alignment of total robotic practice, standardised operative delivery, embedded training, and digitally enabled recovery. Our key lesson is that robotic surgery cannot be evaluated in isolation. High-performing programmes matter most, but platforms that facilitate standardisation, efficiency, and reproducibility may further enhance those gains.

We do recognise that important barriers remain to replicating this model. Capital expenditure is substantial, theatre capacity is constrained, a generation of surgical trainees reports 70% with no robotic exposure during formative years, and equity of access across different trust settings presents fundamental challenges.⁸ These obstacles require systemic change at a national level. WHTH has demonstrated what can be achieved when these elements align, while also illustrating how much institutional development remains necessary before this becomes standard practice across the NHS.

Figure 5. The robotic surgery team at West Hertfordshire Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust.

Conflicts of interest: Mr Vanash Patel is a preceptor for CMR Surgical and a proctor for Intuitive Surgical.

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